

IPBES TCA Chapter 3. Review of knowledge on theories and frameworks of transformative change / IPBES transformative change assessment

Third emerging list of relevant references on theories and frameworks

Cluster 1: Science and technology

- Ecomodernist manifesto (Asafu-Adjaye et al., 2015): DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.1974.0646
- Ecological modernization: Mol, A.P.J., and Sonnenfeld, D.A., (eds.) 2000, Ecological Modernisation around the World: Perspectives and Critical Debates, London and Portland, OR, Frank Cass/ Routledge, ISBN 978-0-7146-8113-9.
- Innovation Studies (Schot and Steinmueller, 2018): Three frames for innovation policy: R&D, systems of innovation and transformative change.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.08.011>
- Social Innovation (Adanella Rossi): THE TRANSFORMATIVE POTENTIAL OF SOCIAL INNOVATION. THE CASE OF WHEAT AND BREAD VALUE CHAIN IN TUSCANY:
<https://doi.org/10.48416/ijisaf.v24i3.5>
- Mission Innovation (Mariana Mazzucato): 2017: Mission-Oriented Innovation Policy Challenges and opportunities by Mariana Mazzucato ISBN 978-1-911532-09-5.
- TRANSFORMATION OF INDUSTRIAL, TECHNOLOGICAL AND ORGANIZATION-AL AND INSTITUTIONAL STRUCTURES OF THE COUNTRY ECONOMY IN THE CONDITIONS OF INTEGRATION PROCESSES OF GLOBALIZATION. December 2018. International Journal of New Economics and Social Sciences 8(2):3-11. DOI:10.5604/01.3001.0012.9924
- Handbook of science and technology studies. Fox 1995.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412990127>

Cluster 2: Knowledge Co-Creation

- Chambers et al. 2022. Co-productive agility and four collaborative pathways to sustainability transformations. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102422>
- Lang Wiek 2022: Structuring and advancing solution-oriented research for sustainability. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13280-021-01537-7>
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- Wyborn, C., Davila, F., Pereira, L. et al. (2020) Imagining transformative biodiversity futures. Nature Sustainability. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-0587-5>
- Rapidly shifting environmental baselines among fishers of the Gulf of California. Andrea Sáenz-Arroyo, CallumM Roberts, Jorge Torre, Micheline Cariño-Olvera and RobertoR Enríquez-Andrade. Published:22 September 2005 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2005.3175>
- König 2015: Changing requisites to universities in the 21st century: organizing for transformative sustainability science for systemic change. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2015.08.011>

- Horlings et al. 2020: Operationalising transformative sustainability science through place-based research: the role of researchers. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11625-019-00757-x>
- Brandt et al. 2013: A review of transdisciplinary research in sustainability science. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2013.04.008>
- Jahn, T., M. Bergmann, F. Keil. 2012. Transdisciplinarity: Between mainstreaming and marginalization. *Ecological Economics* 79: 1 – 10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2012.04.017>.
- Bergmann et al. 2021: Transdisciplinary sustainability research in real-world labs: success factors and methods for change. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11625-020-00886-8>

Cluster 3: Systems

- Berkes Turner 2006: Knowledge, Learning and the Evolution of Conservation Practice for Social-Ecological System Resilience. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10745-006-9008-2>
- A Theory of Transformative Agency in Linked Social-Ecological Systems. Frances R. Westley, Ola Tjornbo, Lisen Schultz, Per Olsson, Carl Folke, Beatrice Crona, Örjan Bodin. *Ecology and Society*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26269375>
- Berkes et al. 2009: Navigating Social-Ecological Systems. Building Resilience for Complexity and Change. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511541957>
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- Abson et al. 2017: Leverage points for sustainability transformation. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13280-016-0800-y>
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- Sachet et al. 2021: Agroecological Transitions: A Systematic Review of Research Approaches and Prospects for Participatory Action Methods. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2021.709401>
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Cluster 4: Inner transformations

- Woiwode et al. 2021: Inner transformation to sustainability as a deep leverage point: fostering new avenues for change through dialogue and reflection. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11625-020-00882-y>
- Grenni et al. 2020: The inner dimension of sustainability transformation: how sense of place and values can support sustainable place-shaping. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11625-019-00743-3>
- Ives et al. 2023: IMAGINE sustainability: integrated inner-outer transformation in research, education and practice. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11625-023-01368-3>
- Wamsler et al. 2021: Linking internal and external transformation for sustainability and climate action: Towards a new research and policy agenda. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102373>
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- Horcea-Milcu et al. 2019: Values in transformational sustainability science: four perspectives for change. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11625-019-00656-1>

Cluster 5: Empowerment

- Ray et al. 2022: Power and empowerment of grassroots innovations for sustainability transitions: A review. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2022.04.009>
- Seyfang et al. 2015: What influences the diffusion of grassroots innovations for sustainability? Investigating community currency niches. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2015.1063603>
- Leach et al. 1999: Environmental Entitlements: Dynamics and Institutions in Community-Based Natural Resource Management Empowerment approaches
- Stirling et al. 2007: Empowering Designs: towards more progressive social appraisal of sustainability. <https://opendocs.ids.ac.uk/opendocs/handle/20.500.12413/2473>
- Crowley et al. 2020: Engaging and empowering people in biodiversity conservation: lessons from practice. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.3318/bioe.2020.15>
- Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021: Transformative governance of biodiversity: insights for sustainable development. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2021.06.002>
- Bass and Bass 2008: The Bass Handbook of Leadership: Theory, Research, and Managerial Applications
- Mies, Shiva 2014: Ecofeminism.
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- Simpson 2016: Indigenous Resurgence and Co-resistance. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5749/jcritethnstud.2.2.0019>
- Schlosberg 2013: Theorising environmental justice: the expanding sphere of a discourse. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2013.755387>
- Dawson et al. 2017: Environmental justice research shows the importance of social feedbacks in ecosystem service trade-offs. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26270153>
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- Brown, Westaway 2011: Agency, Capacity, and Resilience to Environmental Change: Lessons from Human Development, Well-Being, and Disasters. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-052610-092905>

Cluster 6: Structural approaches

- Duit et al. 2015: Greening Leviathan: the rise of the environmental state?. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2015.1085218>
- Eckersley 2004: The Green State: Rethinking Democracy and Sovereignty. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/3364.001.0001>
- Eckersley 2021: Greening states and societies: from transitions to great transformations. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2020.1810890>
- Sterner et al. 2019: Policy design for the Anthropocene. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41893-018-0194-x>
- Behavioural economics (Alpizar et al., 2022)
- Visseren-Hamakers et al. 2021: Transformative governance of biodiversity: insights for sustainable development. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2021.06.002>
- Gilpin 2016: The Political Economy of International Relations. ISBN 0691022623
- Newell 2021: Power shift: The global political economy of energy transitions
- Calderón-Contreras et al. 2021: A regional PECS node built from place-based social-ecological sustainability research in Latin America and the Caribbean. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2021.2000501>

- ecological civilization framework (refs need to be checked); Governmentality (Foucault?, Additional refs); Policy Advocacy Theories (Sabatier, Keck and Sikkink, E. Schlager); Political/Institutional Alignment theories (R. Rogowski)